

DAMAGE ACCUMULATION IN GRAPHITE/EPOXY LAMINATES DUE TO CYCLIC GRADIENT STRESS FIELDS

Paul A. Lagace and Kenneth J. Bonello*
TECHNOLOGY LABORATORY FOR ADVANCED COMPOSITES
Department of Aeronautics and Astronautics
Massachusetts Institute of Technology
Cambridge, MA 02139

ABSTRACT

The progression of damage in gradient stress fields under cyclic loading was studied in simply-supported graphite/epoxy beam-columns. Three layups, $[45_4/-45_4/(0/90)_4]_{2S}$, $[\pm 45/0/90]_{4S}$, and $[(45_2/-45_2/0)_2/90_5]_{2S}$, were chosen to be consistent with data collected in a previous study with static loading. Specimens were loaded statically until predetermined characteristic damage levels were obtained, after which cyclic loading began. At specific intervals, cyclic loading was stopped, a static test measuring the load and the corresponding center deflection was performed, and edge replicas of the specimen's sides were taken. The damage of these specimens varied both along the length and through the thickness of the specimens with two general modes of damage present. Damage due to the static loading generally occurred on the tension side of the specimen and was controlled by matrix cracks. Delaminations initiated and grew in areas of crack saturation. Damage due to the cyclic loading also occurred on the compression side of the specimens and was controlled by delaminations which initiated and grew independently of matrix cracks, leading to sublaminar buckling. Increasing the maximum cyclic load changed the relative growth of the two modes of damage, thus changing the final failure mode.

KEYWORDS: Damage accumulation, delamination, fatigue, gradient field

1. INTRODUCTION

The damage growth and fatigue behavior of composite materials has been extensively studied [e.g. 1-7]. Most work, however, has not considered the effects of gradient stress fields, except for the case of holes. Gradient stress fields are

* currently at General Motors Corporation

important in the application of composite structures including simple bending fields as well as more complicated responses. For example, the prebuckled and postbuckled response of structures involve gradient stress fields in both the longitudinal and through-thickness directions. The lack of understanding of the effects of damage on the performance of composite structures hampers their use in the postbuckled regime, where additional load-carrying capacity exists, as well as in other applications. It is thus important to understand how damage modes initiate and interact in such cyclic gradient stress fields and how the fatigue performance is affected by this damage.

Fatigue life of composites has frequently been characterized by S-N curves [e.g. 8]. It is apparent [9] that simple characterizations such as S-N curves cannot, however, adequately describe the response of composites to cyclic load due to the complex and diverse damage types which occur. It is therefore necessary to study the damage mechanisms and interactive damage accumulation which occur under cyclic loading [e.g. 10,11]. Results from such work clearly show that multiple failure modes can exist for laminates under cyclic loading, with some of these modes different from those exhibited under static loading [12,13].

The objective of this work, therefore, is to investigate the damage accumulation in graphite/epoxy laminates due to cyclic gradient stress fields. This damage development is to be compared to that which occurs under static loading as well as that which occurs for various cyclic stress levels in order to begin to develop an understanding of the effect the cyclic gradient stress field may have.

2. APPROACH

Work has previously been conducted [14] on the progression of damage in simply-supported beam-column specimens under quasi-static loading. The specimen configuration and test jig used in the previous work, shown in Figure 1, was adopted for this investigation. The specimen has a length of 200 mm and a width of 37.5 mm.

This specimen meets three important requirements. One, the stress state is relatively simple in that it varies sinusoidally in the longitudinal direction and linearly through-the-thickness (ignoring transverse shear effects). Two, the location of damage is predictable in that the maximum stress occurs at the longitudinal center of the specimen, away from the points of load introduction. And three, the damage progression is observable since matrix cracks and delamination are evident at the free edges of the specimen.

The test jig loads the specimen 2.54 mm off the specimen centerline. This loading eccentricity allows any friction in the jig to be overcome so that simply-supported response occurs. Furthermore, the magnitude of this eccentricity is greater than possible manufacturing imperfections in the laminate thus making the response insensitive to these imperfections. The total length of the column including the 200 mm test specimen and end pieces is 224 mm.

FIGURE 1 Configuration of (left) test specimen, and (right) specimen in test jig.

Three configurations of laminates were chosen: $[\pm 45/0/90_4]_4S$, $[(45_2/-45_2/0)_2/90_5]_2S$, and $[45_4/-45_4/(0/90)_4]_2S$. These laminates, used in the previous work, model laminates commonly used in the aerospace industry with 0° , $\pm 45^\circ$, and 90° orientations. Large effective ply thicknesses were utilized so that damage under static loading would initially occur in these plies in the form of matrix cracks. Groups of plies with the same fiber orientations behave as a single ply in that a matrix crack will propagate through the entire thickness of the ply and delaminations do not occur within such a ply group. For this reason, such a group of plies is considered as a single "effective ply" [15].

All specimens were made from Hercules AS4/3501-6 graphite/epoxy with a nominal per ply thickness of 0.134 mm. This yielded nominal laminate thicknesses of 7.50 mm, 8.04 mm, and 8.58 mm for the $[\pm 45/0/90_4]_4S$, $[(45_2/-45_2/0)_2/90_5]_2S$, and $[45_4/-45_4/(0/90)_4]_2S$ laminates, respectively.

A test program, summarized in Table 1, was designed to determine the damage accumulation history of the three layups when subjected to static and cyclic loading. Specimens of each layup were tested statically to failure. These tests were interrupted and edge replicas taken such that a damage accumulation history could be pieced together. Center deflection versus load measurements were also recorded in order to produce Southwell plots which provide a comparative measure of the specimen stiffness as damage accumulates. The specimens tested cyclically were first damaged to a predetermined level in static loading. The four characteristic damage states/levels noted for these layups under static loading [16] were used to define the initial damage levels desired before cyclic loading.

TABLE 1 Test Matrix

Layup	Static Tests	Cyclic tests ^a with Predamage Level ^b			
		1	1+	3	3+
[45 ₄ /-45 ₄ /(0/90) ₄] _{2S}	4 ^c	7	-	-	-
[±45/0/90 ₄] _{4S}	2	4	-	3	3
[(45 ₂ /-45 ₂ /0) ₂ /90 ₅] _{2S}	2	2	2	3/3 ^d	-

^a R value equals 10 in all cases.

^b Predamage levels correspond to static characteristic damage states. Maximum load corresponds to predamage load level unless indicated.

^c Number indicates number of specimens tested.

^d Three specimens loaded at level 1 maximum load.

The cyclic tests were conducted with an R value of 10 and various values of the maximum load. The tests were halted at predetermined test intervals (every 2500 cycles for the first four intervals and 5000 cycles thereafter), edge replicas taken, and a static test sequence performed in which load versus center deflection were measured. This allowed the monitoring of the accumulation of damage and relative stiffness degradation with respect to the number of cycles.

3. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

A total of 12 specimens of each laminate configuration were manufactured. Laminates (350 mm by 305 mm) of each laminate type were cured in an autoclave under 0.59 MPa pressure and full vacuum (760 mm Hg) following the manufacturer's recommended cycle of one hour at 116°C followed by two hours at 177°C. All laminates were postcured in an unpressurized oven for eight hours at 177°C. Each laminate was machined into 37.5 mm by 200 mm specimens using a water-cooled diamond-grit cutting wheel. The specimen edges were polished with a 25 mm diameter felt bob soaked in a colloidal solution of Kaopolite SF, a mild abrasive with an average particle size of 0.7 μm.

All tests were carried out on an MTS 810 Material Testing System. Static tests were conducted at a stroke rate of 0.0254 mm per second using the Load Drop Technique [17]. The specimens are loaded in displacement control and the detection of a drop in compressive load is interpreted as the possible occurrence of damage. Edge replicas of the specimen were taken at each load drop while the specimen was still under load. Previous work [14] indicated that the development of damage across the width of the specimen was relatively uniform thus negating the need to perform additional examination in this work. The specimens were reloaded after completion of the edge replicating process. In addition, transverse center deflection versus load data was taken via a deflection transducer.

Cyclic tests were run in load control with a function generator providing the waveform for the haversine loading at a frequency of 1.5 Hz. Several specimens

FIGURE 2 Typical (left) edge replica, and (right) its transcription.

were instrumented with a thermocouple on the specimen surface center. No significant increases in temperature were noted throughout the duration of the tests. This frequency was thus considered safe for all the tests. The cyclic loading was halted at the predetermined intervals and a static test performed to assess the stiffness of the specimen, via Southwell buckling loads calculated from load versus transverse center deflection data, and the damage state of the specimen, via edge replicas. All tests were conducted to failure defined as the inability of the specimen to carry at least 50% of the maximum load. Failures were catastrophic in nearly every case.

A microscope, at a magnification of thirty, was used to examine the replicas. When these replicas are examined under a microscope with backlighting, matrix cracks and delaminations can easily be observed. The damage as seen on the replicas was transcribed to schematics of the specimen edge. These schematics are originally drawn to scale along the length of the specimen and expanded by a factor of about seven through-the-thickness with each effective ply identified separately. Cracks and delaminations are drawn on the appropriate plies. A photograph of a typical replica along with the corresponding transcription is shown in Figure 2. The key shown in Figure 3 is used for all cases. The damage was generally symmetric about the longitudinal centerline, so only the left half of transcriptions are subsequently shown. The side of the specimen exhibiting the greatest tensile stresses due to bending is referred to as the tension side and is placed at the top of each replica, with the other side is referred to as the compression side.

FIGURE 3 Key for all replica transcriptions.

4. RESULTS

For each laminate and set of loading metrics, typical damage progressions are presented. Final failures are also shown. In all cases, the tension side of the laminate is at the right of the photograph. Important loads are summarized in Table 2: the maximum loads at which cycling takes place and the Southwell buckling loads measured in the static tests with the specimens at the reported damage level. Further details are available in Reference 18.

4.1 [45₄/-45₄/(0/90)₄]₂S Laminate The damage progression under static loading for this laminate is shown in Figure 4. This can be contrasted to the typical damage progression under cyclic loading, shown in Figure 5, for these specimens initially damaged to the first damage state consisting of matrix cracking in the outermost tension-side +45° and -45° effective plies. Under static loading, the crack density in these plies increased and delaminations began to form at the +45°/-45° interface between matrix cracks. These delaminations grew together and propagated towards the specimen ends only in regions of matrix cracks. Similar damage occurred under cyclic loading, but delamination also initiated on the outermost +45°/-45° interface on the compression side approximately halfway to failure. It is noteworthy that the initiation and growth of this delamination was independent of matrix cracks as the delamination did not terminate at matrix cracks. In contrast, tension-side delaminations always initiated and terminated at matrix cracks.

These damage sequences resulted in different final failure modes for the static and cyclic cases as can be seen in Figure 6. Final failure under static loading was restricted to the tension side on the laminate while both the tension and compression sides were involved in the cyclic case. Cyclic failure occurred in the range of 2,000-35,000 cycles.

TABLE 2 Important Experimental Loads^a

Static Characteristic Damage State/Level	Laminate					
	[45 ₄ /-45 ₄ /(0/90) ₄] ₂ S		[±45/0/90 ₄] ₄ S		[(45 ₂ /-45 ₂ /0) ₂ /90 ₅] ₂ S	
	M ^b	S ^c	M	S	M	S
0	-	18.4	-	8.6	-	12.6
1	12.8	17.5	6.9	8.3	8.7	12.4
2	-	17.5	-	8.3	-	12.2
3	-	17.4	7.7	8.3	9.1	12.1
4	-	17.0	-	8.0	-	11.9
Failure	13.1	-	7.1	-	9.3	-

^a All loads in kN.

^b Indicates average load level needed to attain damage and used as maximum load in cyclic tests.

^c Indicates average Southwell buckling load for specimens with that damage level.

FIGURE 4 Damage history of a typical $[45_4/-45_4/(0/90)_4]_{2S}$ specimen tested statically.

FIGURE 5 Damage history of a typical $[45_4/-45_4/(0/90)_4]_{2S}$ specimen tested cyclically with initial damage at the first level.

FIGURE 6 Typical failed $[45_4/-45_4/(0/90)_4]_{2S}$ specimen (*left*) tested statically, and (*right*) tested cyclically with initial damage at the first level.

4.2 $[\pm 45/0/90_4]_{4S}$ Laminate The damage progression under static loading is shown in Figure 7 with matrix cracks initiating in the outermost tension-side 90° ply. This is followed by short, discontinuous delaminations which link matrix cracks. These delaminations grow to form one continuous delamination. Despite the fact that all the observable damage is on the tension side, failure occurs with sublaminates buckling on the compression side of the specimen as can be seen in Figure 11. In the previous work [14], failure in this specimen under static load was restricted to the tension side of the laminate. This indicates that these specimens represent a borderline situation where a slight change in specimen thickness or material properties can trigger a specific damage mode and influence the failure.

FIGURE 7 Damage history of a typical $[\pm 45/0/90_4]_{4S}$ specimen tested statically.

FIGURE 8 Damage history of a typical $[\pm 45/0/90_4]_{4S}$ specimen tested cyclically with initial damage at the first level.

FIGURE 9 Damage history of a typical $[\pm 45/0/90_4]_{4S}$ specimen tested cyclically at maximum load of 7.7 kN with initial damage at the third level.

FIGURE 10 Damage history of a typical $[\pm 45/0/90_4]_{4S}$ specimen tested cyclically at maximum load of 7.9 kN with initial damage just beyond the third level.

Damage progression under cyclic loading is shown in Figures 8, 9, and 10. A similar pattern occurred on the tension side of the specimen, but once again, damage occurred in the form of delamination on the compression side of the specimen at the outermost $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interface. These delaminations were, again, not necessarily associated with matrix cracks. This compression side damage did generally progress more rapidly than the tension-side damage in the latter portions of the tests with gross delaminations visible to the naked eye just before failure.

FIGURE 11 Typical failed $[\pm 45/0/90_4]_{4S}$ specimen (a) tested statically, (b) tested cyclically with initial damage at the first level, (c) tested cyclically at 7.7 kN with initial damage at the third level, and (d) tested cyclically at 7.9 kN with initial damage just beyond the third level.

This was true for both the specimens initially damaged to the first and third damage state. The only discernible difference between these cases was a reduction in the life range of the specimens from 46,000-63,000 cycles to 30,000-52,000 cycles. This is likely also attributable to the higher load level of 7.7 kN versus 6.9 kN for the specimens initially damaged to the first damage state. Both types of specimens failed both on the tension and compression sides as can be seen in Figure 11.

However, three specimens were damaged just beyond the third damage state in that the delamination at the tension-side $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interface was virtually continuous. These specimens were also cycled at a slightly higher maximum load of 7.9 kN. This resulted in a reduced lifetime range of 4,000-14,000 cycles and a very different failure mode, shown in Figure 11, where final failure occurred only on the tension side of the specimen. Apparently, the tension side damage extended further in these specimens and became more critical than the compression-side damage. This slight increase in loading therefore changed the final failure and significantly reduced the lifetime of the specimen.

4.3 $[(45_2/-45_2/0)_2/90_5]_{2S}$ Laminate The static damage progression for this laminate, shown in Figure 12, indicates matrix cracking initiated in the outermost tension-side 90° effective ply. Short, discontinuous delaminations formed at the

FIGURE 12 Damage history of a typical $[(45_2/-45_2/0)_2/90_5]_{2S}$ specimen tested statically.

FIGURE 13 Damage history of a typical $[(45_2/-45_2/0)_2/90_5]_2S$ specimen tested cyclically at maximum load of 8.7 kN with initial damage at the first level.

FIGURE 14 Damage history of a typical $[(45_2/-45_2/0)_2/90_5]_2S$ specimen tested cyclically at maximum load of 10.1 kN with initial damage just beyond the first level.

FIGURE 15 Damage history of a typical $[(45_2/-45_2/0)_2/90_5]_2S$ specimen tested cyclically at maximum load of 9.1 kN with initial damage at the third level.

FIGURE 16 Damage history of a typical $[(45_2/-45_2/0)_2/90_5]_2S$ specimen tested cyclically at maximum load of 8.7 kN with initial damage at the third level.

$0^\circ/90^\circ$ interface linking these cracks and eventually grew and became continuous. Some discontinuous delaminations also occurred later in the loading at the $90^\circ/+45^\circ$ interface linking matrix cracks. Final failure occurred with the rapid occurrence of delaminations along the midthickness 90° ply and the tension-side $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interfaces with the compression side remaining intact as seen in Figure 17.

The damage which occurred in the static loading case also occurred in all cyclic loading cases as seen in Figures 13 through 16. In addition, the outermost $+45^\circ/-45^\circ$ interfaces on both the tension and compression sides delaminated in these cases with subsequent matrix cracking in the adjoining plies. In two cases, final failure occurred on both the tension and compression sides: the specimens initially damaged to the first damage level with a maximum load of 8.7 kN and those initially damaged to the third damage level also cycled at a maximum load of 8.7 kN. These two groups of specimens had lifetimes of 600,000 cycles and 12,000-29,000 cycles, respectively.

The two other groups of specimens were cycled at higher maximum loads: those initially damaged just beyond the first damage state at 10.1 kN and those initially damaged to the third damage state at 9.1 kN. These specimens had lifetime ranges of 8,500-53,000 cycles and 5,000-29,000 cycles, respectively. Not only did these specimens have shorter lifetimes, but the damage progression shows that the damage on the compression side occurs much later in the life and to a lesser extent resulting in their failures being restricted to the tension side, as can be seen in Figure 17. This is in contrast to their counterparts cycled at lower loads where failure occurred throughout the specimen.

4.4 General Characteristics of Damage Accumulation Static loading generally caused damage to initiate only on the tension side of the specimen at the longitudinal center of the specimen in the outermost effective plies of greatest

FIGURE 17 Typical failed $[(45_2/-45_2/0)_2/90_5]_2S$ specimen (a) tested statically, (b) tested cyclically at 8.7 kN with initial damage at the first level, (c) tested cyclically at 10.1 kN with initial damage just beyond the first level, (d) tested cyclically at 9.1 kN with initial damage at the third level, and (e) tested cyclically at 8.7 kN with initial damage at the third level.

thickness. This initial damage was in the form of in-plane matrix cracks. Delaminations formed at these matrix cracks and linked up to form a continuous delamination prior to failure. The formation of delaminations at the interfaces associated with the cracked plies was related to the stress concentrations at the intersection of the matrix cracks and the ply interface. Final failure was generally limited to the tension side of the specimen except in the $[\pm 45/0/90_4]_{4S}$ specimens as discussed.

In addition to the damage noted in the static case, damage during cyclic loading also occurred on the compression side of the specimens. This delamination initiation and growth was independent of matrix cracking and did not terminate at crack locations. This indicates a different mechanism governing damage initiation and growth due to the cyclic gradient stress field as compared to that due to the static loading. Cyclic loading caused the fatigue/fracture of the interply matrix layer resulting in initiation of delamination without the presence of matrix cracks. As this delamination grows, sublaminar buckling mechanisms can contribute to further growth and eventual failure of the laminate. Laminate failure generally occurs on both the tension and compression sides.

However, this accumulation of damage and final failure mode under cyclic loading depended on the maximum cyclic load level. Specifically, the relative importance of the tension-side and compression-side damage changed. For the specimens cyclically loaded at higher load levels, the dominant failure was the tension-side failure, versus compression-side failure for specimens cyclically loaded at lower load levels. The higher maximum cyclic load level apparently caused the tension-side damage to progress faster than the compression-side damage thus leading to tension-side failure before the compression-side damage became dominant/critical.

The degradation of the stiffness, as measured by Southwell buckling loads, was not significant until just prior to failure. The measured Southwell buckling loads, as shown for all three laminate configurations in Figure 18, generally increased slightly after the start of cyclic loading and then steadily declined throughout the rest of the test. However, the stiffness did not degrade significantly (less than 6%) over most of the cyclic portion of the test. This is attributed to the lack of fiber breakage in the major load-carrying plies (0°). Until the delaminations became large enough to

FIGURE 18 Normalized Southwell buckling loads versus normalized cycle time for (left) $[45_{\mu}/-45_{\mu}/(0/90)_4]_{2S}$ specimens, (center) $[\pm 45/0/90_4]_{4S}$ specimens, and (right) $[(45_2/-45_2/0)_2/90_5]_{2S}$ specimens.

effectively split the specimens into two pieces, the required load-carrying capability of the specimens was maintained. Stiffness would therefore be inadequate as a measure of damage or a warning method for failure for structures under bending. This is consistent with previous findings [e.g. 19].

5. IMPLICATIONS ON TESTING AND STRUCTURAL CERTIFICATION

The evaluation of the behavior of structures under cyclic loads can be very expensive and time consuming. Taking measures to reduce testing time can be significant in economic terms. As a result, some philosophies of structural certification maintain that all critical damage and failure modes are exhibited in static testing. Furthermore, load enhancement factors are also used to reduce testing time.

This investigation shows that cyclic testing under gradient stress fields exposes damage modes not experienced during static testing as compression-side delamination initiated and often controlled final failure. If these laminates were evaluated based on their static tests to failure, their expected behavior under repeated bending would be significantly different that what was actually found. It is therefore important to evaluate structures and their potential damage modes based on cyclic tests results in their actual loading condition.

The test results further indicate that load enhancement factors will not always reveal the same behavior as would be seen in the field. Varying the cyclic load level changes the dominance of competing damage modes. The compression-side damage modes were not the cause of failure for those specimens cyclically loaded at higher levels. Thus, increasing the cyclic load level to reduce testing time could produce a different dominant damage mode and resulting failure mode than would normally occur. Depending on the relationship between the load enhancement factor and the life enhancement factor, there is a potential of overestimating the cyclic lifetime at the lower load level of interest. It is essential that the actual cyclic tests simulate the damage that will grow and potentially cause failure under field conditions.

It is important to note that the maximum loads used in the cyclic testing in this investigation are a large percentage of the ultimate load-carrying capability of the specimens (approximately 90%). This is not typical of load levels in structural applications, particularly in the aerospace industry. These load levels were chosen to reduce testing time. Nonetheless, these high values do not negate the phenomena observed: that different damage modes can be observed under cyclic loading and that changing the cyclic load level can cause the importance of a damage mode to change. These phenomena should be carefully considered and studied at load levels more appropriate to structural application.

6. SUMMARY

A test program to study the damage accumulation in simply-supported graphite/epoxy beam-columns subjected to static and cyclic loading was conducted. Three laminate configurations were utilized: $[45_4/-45_4/(0/90)_4]_{2S}$, $[\pm 45/0/90]_{4S}$, and $[(45_2/-45_2/0)_2/90_5]_{2S}$. Damage accumulation histories were compiled via edge replicas. The damage due to static loading initiated at the longitudinal center of the specimen in the outermost tension-side effective plies of greatest thickness. This damage was in the form of matrix cracks. Delaminations subsequently occurred at the matrix cracks/ply interface intersections. Final failure generally occurred on the tension side of the specimen. Under cyclic loading, delamination also occurred on the compression side of the specimen. This delamination was independent of matrix cracks indicating a different mechanism controlled its initiation and growth. Final failure in the cyclic case often includes a compression-side component.

The results clearly show that cyclic loading reveals critical damage modes not found under static loading. Furthermore, the maximum cyclic load can change the dominant failure mode when competing modes exist. Thus, cyclic loading should be used when ascertaining all possible damage modes. The use of load enhancement factors and higher cyclic load levels to reduce testing time could hide critical damage modes with the potential of overestimating cyclic lifetime.

However, the cyclic load levels utilized in this work were a large fraction (approximately 90%) of the ultimate load-carrying capability of the specimens. Further work should be done to study these phenomena at load levels more characteristic of cyclic loads found in actual structures.

7. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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9. BIOGRAPHIES

Dr. Paul A. Lagace is a Leaders for Manufacturing Associate Professor of Aeronautics and Astronautics at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology. He received his S.B. (1978), S.M. (1979), and Ph.D. (1982) from M.I.T. and then joined the faculty. He is currently the Director of the Technology Laboratory for Advanced Composites where he conducts research on composite materials and structures, especially their fracture, damage resistance, arrest, and tolerance, and longevity characteristics. In addition to SAMPE, he is a member of the American Society for Composites, AIAA, and ASTM, where he is an Executive Committee member of Committee D30 on High Modulus Fibers and their Composites.

Kenneth J. Bonello is a project engineer at General Motors Corporation. He received his B.S. in mechanical engineering from GMI Engineering & Management Institute (1988) and S.M. in aeronautics and astronautics at M.I.T. (1990). He is currently conducting research in analytical tool development for occupant safety and vehicle crashworthiness. He is a member of SAE.

